
POPULATION DYNAMICS, ITS TYPES. POPULATION MIGRATION (EXTERNAL, INTERNAL) FACTORS DETERMINING IT MAIN TRENDS IMPACT OF MIGRATION ON POPULATION

¹Moldoev Murzali Ilyazovich , ²Maharaja Sre Varshine, ³Harshvardhan Sanjay mane

^{*1}Teacher, Department of Public Health, International Medical Faculty, Osh State University, Osh, Kyrgyzstan

^{*2}Medical Student, International Medical Faculty, Osh State University, Osh, Kyrgyzstan.

^{*3}Medical Student, International Medical Faculty, Osh State University, Osh, Kyrgyzstan.

ABSTRACT

This Article explores concept of Population Dynamics and The Role of migration in shaping population structures with a focus on external and internal migration. It highlights key factors influencing migration and major global trends. The impact of migration on population size, structure and developments is also discussed.

Keywords: Population dynamics, Migration.

INTRODUCTION

Population dynamics and Migration are pivotal concepts in demographic studies, reflecting the patterns of population growth, distribution, and structure. In the field of public health, population dynamics is important because it allows to understand the spread of diseases and impact of diseases in different population and to gain insights into factors that affect rates of diseases. It encompasses the factors that influence population size, such as birth rates, death rates, and migration. Migration-both external and internal-plays a major role in shaping these dynamics. People move for various reasons including economic opportunities, environmental changes, conflicts and social factors. As global mobility increases understanding the factors migration and its effects on population trends has become more important than ever. Understanding the factors and its broader implications is essential for comprehending contemporary population trends.

POPULATION DYNAMICS

Population dynamics refers to the study of how populations change over time including the growth, decline and distribution of population. These changes are influenced by factors such as

- ❖ Birth Rates,
 - ❖ Death Rates,
 - ❖ Immigration and Emigration
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TYPES OF POPULATION DYNAMICS

STABLE POPULATION:

- A population that remains relatively constant over time. The age structure is stable.
- **Birth rates are roughly equal to death rates. ZERO GROWTH OR EQUILIBRIUM**

GROWING POPULATION:

- EXPONENTIAL GROWTH - Occurs when a population **grows at constant rate over time**, leading to rapid increase in population size. Happens when resources are abundant and environmental factors are not limiting.
- LOGISTIC GROWTH - Pattern occurs when a population reaches the carrying capacities that is the maximum population size that environment can support

POPULATION DECLINE:

- NEGATIVE GROWTH RATE - Occurs when **death rate exceeds birth rates** leading to reduction in population size. Result from factors like increasing mortality rates or lowering fertility, emigration rates.
- POPULATION EXTINCTION - Extinction is ultimate form of population decline, where a population **decreases to zero** due to unsustainable exploitation

POPULATION FLUCTUATION:

- CYCLIC FLUTUATION - Population size may **fluctuate in cycles** due to periodic environmental changes, availability of resources.
- RANDOM FLUCTUATION - **Fluctuate irregularly** due to unpredictable factors such as disease outbreaks, natural disasters.

POPULATION STRUTURAL CHANGES:

- **AGE STRUCTURE** - Changes in the age distribution can impact the dynamics of the population. A population with a large proportion of elderly experience a decline in numbers over time whereas a youthful population grow rapidly.
- **SEX RATIO** - The ratio of males to females in a population influence population dynamics.

DEMOGRAPHIC TRANSITION:

- STAGE 1- Pre-Industrial stage: High birth and death rates lead to a stable or slow growing population. This stage is typically characterized by **high infant mortality and limited access**.
- STAGE 2- Transitional stage: **Death rates decline** due to improvement in healthcare but **birth rates remain high** leading to rapid population growth.
- STAGE 3- Industrial stage: **Birth rates decline** due to urbanization.
- STAGE 4- Post-Industrial stage: **Both birth and death rate are low**, leading to slow growing population. High living standards widespread education are common.

One of the key reasons why understanding population dynamics is essential is its direct impact on resource allocation

Furthermore, understanding population dynamics is crucial for effective urban planning

Finally, understanding population dynamics can help us address pressing global issues, such as climate change and sustainable development

POPULATION MIGRATION

Migration refers to the movement of people from one place to another. It can be of two and influenced by any factors by directly impacting the size, composition and distribution of populations in both the areas people leave and the areas they move to

TYPES OF MIGRATION

EXTERNAL MIGRATION: International migration that is movement of people from one country to another. It can be;

- ❖ **EMIGRATION**- The act of leaving one's home country to live in another country
- ❖ **IMMIGRATION**- The act of entering a foreign Country to live there.

INTERNAL MIGRATION: Refers to the movement of people within the same country typically from rural to urban areas but it can also happen between regions or provinces. It can be;

- ❖ **URBAN TO RURAL-** It is the most common form for better job opportunities, education, healthcare and living standards in cities.
- ❖ **RURAL TO URBAN-** Not common but happens when people migrate seeking a slower pace of life, lower cost of living or to escape overcrowding.

MAIN TRENDS IN MIGRATION

- 1. URBANIATION:** One of the most significant global migration trends. As more people move to cities urban population grows rapidly leading to expansion urban centres. This trend is particularly prevalent in developing countries.
- 2. INTERNATIONAL MIGRATION:** Economic migrants refugees continue to migrate globally to greater distances in search of economic opportunities safety or for better living. Migration to developed countries is particularly high from less developed countries in Africa, Asia, and Latin America.

International migrant population in ___, in millions

3. **ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE MIGRATION:** Environmental factors such as extreme weather sea level rise and environmental degradation increasingly affects migration patterns.

4. **RETURN MIGRATION:** Some migrants after spending years abroad choose to return to home countries due to improved conditions, personal reasons or changes in immigration policies of host countries.

IMPACT OF MIGRATION ON POPULATION

- ❖ **Loss of labour force**
- ❖ **Demographic changes**
- ❖ **Cultural and Social effects**
- ❖ **Strain on Resources**

CONCLUSION

Population dynamics and migration are integral to understanding the changing nature of human populations. Driven by variety of social, environmental, economic and political factors, migration shapes demographic trends and presents both opportunities and challenges for regions of origin and destination. As global movement continues to rise a comprehensive understanding of these dynamics for essential for effective planning policy making and sustainable development.

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